

One step process for starch fermentation employing the starch digesting yeast *Saccharomyces diastaticus*

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Abstract : The production of industrial and fuel ethanol from starchy biomass commonly involves three steps. The present investigation was to assess the possibility of developing a direct one step process for starch fermentation employing the starch digesting yeast *Saccharomyces diastaticus*, a haploid strain. Direct fermentation of cassava waste by a pure culture of *S. diastaticus* produced the maximum of 17 g/L ethanol at 36 h fermentation.

Keywords : One step process, fermentation, *Saccharomyces diastaticus*, cassava waste.

Introduction

Starchy materials used in ethanol production are cassava, maize, wheat, barley, oat, sorghum, rice and potatoes. But cassava and corn are the two major substrates of interest. It has been estimated that 11.7 kg of corn starch can be converted into about seven liters of ethanol. Starch is one of the best substrates for alcohol production. It is not capable of being fermented directly by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and so the pretreatment is required for alcohol production. Cassava contains more than 50% starch. It can be grown in very tropical lands and may be considered as a primary alternative to maize and other grains that are used as distillery feed stocks. Panchal *et al.*¹ have shown that *Saccharomyces diastaticus* is more appropriate than a non-amyolytic strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* or the fermentation of starch hydrolyzed by conventional methods. By using *S. diastaticus* Whitney *et al.*² achieved a 50% savings in the glucoamylase concentration which is normally used in the commercial processes for the production of ethanol from starch. Recently a comparative study on ethanol production from molasses using *S. cerevisiae* and *Z. mobilis* was also carried out³.

The production of industrial and fuel ethanol from starchy biomass commonly involves three steps viz. (i) liquefaction of starch by an endoamylase such as α -amylase, (ii) enzymatic saccharification of the low molecular weight liquefaction products (dextrins) to produce glucose and (iii) fermentation of glucose. Commercial en-

zymes are used for liquefaction and saccharification and represent a significant expense in the production process. The present investigation was to assess the possibility of developing a direct one step process for starch fermentation employing the starch digesting yeast *Saccharomyces diastaticus*.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the results of reducing sugar, biomass and ethanol production with pure and mixed fermentation of *S. diastaticus* and *Z. mobilis*. The biggest increment in the reducing sugar content observed in the pure culture of *S. diastaticus* was between 24 and 36 fermentation hours and the maximum 43.76 g/L reducing sugar was observed at 36 h fermentation. Reducing sugar levels of mixed coculture fermentation dropped continuously reaching very small values compared to the pure culture of *S. diastaticus* fermentation. In simultaneously inoculated mixed culture fermentation, the reducing sugar (8.16 g/L) content was very low at 60 h. Similar observations were recorded by Abate *et al.*⁴ with ethanol production by a mixed culture of flocculent strains of *Zymomonas mobilis* and *Saccharomyces* sp.

All the mixed processes reached higher value of biomass than the single fermentation process. A maximum of 20% increase in biomass content was obtained in the 36 h phasing fermentation. Mixed cultures have been used to produce microbial biomass from other starchy materials⁵.

Note

Table 1. Submerged fermentation of cassava waste (100 g/L) by pure and mixed cultures of *Saccharomyces diastaticus* and *Zymomonas mobilis*

(Results are mean \pm SE of three replicates)

Organisms	Period of fermentation (h)					
	0	12	24	36	48	60
	Reducing sugar (g/L)					
A	1.13 \pm 0.1	11.78 \pm 1.1	15.56 \pm 1.4	43.76 \pm 3.9	41.6 \pm 3.7	40.40 \pm 3.6
B		15.32 \pm 1.3	13.68 \pm 1.2	11.48 \pm 1.0	9.68 \pm 0.7	8.15 \pm 0.7
C			12.58 \pm 1.2	12.08 \pm 1.2	11.38 \pm 1.1	11.02 \pm 1.2
D				15.96 \pm 1.3	15.38 \pm 1.6	15.08 \pm 1.3
E					29.02 \pm 1.8	16.7 \pm 1.5
	Biomass (g/L)					
A		1.92 \pm 0.1	2.18 \pm 0.2	2.67 \pm 0.2	2.82 \pm 0.1	2.91 \pm 0.2
B		2.28 \pm 0.2	2.67 \pm 0.1	3.12 \pm 0.2	3.24 \pm 0.2	3.38 \pm 0.2
C			2.3 \pm 0.2	2.87 \pm 0.1	3.34 \pm 0.2	3.27 \pm 0.2
D				2.87 \pm 0.1	3.41 \pm 0.3	3.41 \pm 0.3
E					3.45 \pm 0.2	3.49 \pm 0.2
	Alcohol (g/L)					
A		8.02 \pm 0.5	10.5 \pm 1.0	17.92 \pm 1.6	17.78 \pm 1.6	17.65 \pm 1.3
B		11.26 \pm 0.1	14.66 \pm 1.4	20.42 \pm 2.0	20.72 \pm 2.7	20.56 \pm 2.0
C			13.88 \pm 1.2	18.04 \pm 1.6	17.96 \pm 1.6	17.88 \pm 1.6
D				14.68 \pm 1.4	18.34 \pm 1.5	18.16 \pm 1.6
E					18.7 \pm 1.7	18.48 \pm 1.8

Pure culture A : *S. diastaticus*; Mixed cultures B : Simultaneously inoculation of *S. diastaticus* and *Zymomonas mobilis*; C, D, E : *S. diastaticus* inoculated with *Z. mobilis* after 12, 24 and 36 h of incubation respectively.

Direct fermentation of cassava waste by a pure culture of *S. diastaticus* (a haploid strain) produced the maximum of 17 g/L ethanol at 36 h fermentation. Simultaneous culturing of *S. diastaticus* and *Z. mobilis* resulted in a higher concentration (20.42 g/L at 36 h fermentation). The other mixed fermentations were in between these two values and were obtained either at 36 h or at 48 h fermentation. No significant difference in ethanol production was observed when the yeast was allowed to grow for twelve to thirty six hours before *Z. mobilis* was added. The production of ethanol observed in the submerged fermentation of cassava waste by pure cultures of *S. diastaticus* indicated that these organisms were capable of direct conversion of cassava waste into ethanol. Similarly direct microbial conversion of cellulosic or ligno-cellulosic biomass into ethanol using cocultures had been reported by Khar and Murray⁶.

Christakopoulos *et al.*⁷ and Lezinou *et al.*⁸ reported that the ethanol concentration and yield were significantly enhanced with the mixed cultures of *Fusarium oxysporum* and *S. cerevisiae* compared to the pure culture of the fungus in the direct conversion of sweet sorghum stalk into ethanol and they reported 153.6% theoretical yield

of ethanol while Kallel-Mhiri *et al.*⁹ got 80% theoretical yield in continuous mixed cultures on whey permeate and hydrolyzed starch. The highest percent theoretical yield observed in the present investigation was 91.3% in the mixed cultures of *S. diastaticus* and *Z. mobilis* (Table 2). These results clearly demonstrated that the starch saccharification potential of *S. diastaticus*. But the performance of the later in mixed cultures was significantly higher than their respective pure cultures.

Experimental

Substrate :

Fresh cassava waste was collected from Varalakshmi Sago Industry, Salem, India. It was sun dried, coarsely ground to uniform size (5 mm) and stored in gunny bags and was used within one after procurement.

Organisms :

In the submerged fermentation studies using cassava waste hydrolysate, *Zymomonas mobilis* (NCIM B 806) and *S. diastaticus* (NCIM 3314) were used. The haploid strain of *S. diastaticus* was used. The cultures were procured from National Chemical Laboratory, Pune, India. *Zymomonas mobilis* and *S. diastaticus* were maintained

Table 2. Effect of microbial saccharification on the alcoholic fermentation of cassava waste by *Z. mobilis* (Results are mean \pm SE of three replicates)

Organisms	Fermentation time (h)	Maximum ethanol (g/L)	Maximum biomass (g/L)	Volumetric ethanol productivity	Specific ethanol productivity	Percent theoretical yield
<i>S. diastaticus</i>	36	17.92 \pm 1.6	2.67 \pm 0.2	0.497 \pm 0.03	0.187 \pm 0.01	80.1 \pm 6.0
<i>S. diastaticus</i> + <i>Z. mobilis</i>	36	20.42 \pm 2.0	3.12 \pm 0.2	0.567 \pm 0.04	0.18 \pm 0.01	91.3 \pm 10.0

in rich and MGYB medium respectively. The organisms were stored at 4 °C and subcultured twice a month.

Microbial saccharification and fermentation :

Microbial saccharification and fermentation were carried out using pure and mixed cultures of *S. diastaticus* with *Z. mobilis* as described by Zabala *et al.*¹⁰. Erlenmeyer flasks (250 mL) containing 10 g cassava waste in 100 ml distilled water were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min. Late log phase culture of *S. diastaticus* in MGYB broth was used as inoculum (10% v/v) at a constant OD of 0.5 for the yeast. The flasks were incubated at room temperature (30 \pm 2 °C). The mixed fermentation started with *S. diastaticus* as pure culture and then late log phase culture of *Z. mobilis* (10% v/v) was inoculated either simultaneously or at various time interval (0, 12, 24 and 36). Aliquots were withdrawn at 12 h intervals and assayed for reducing sugars, biomass and ethanol. All the experiments were replicated thrice. The results were tabulated and statistically analyzed.

Analytical method :

Ethanol was measured by the method described by Caputi *et al.*¹¹. Biomass of cells was determined by measuring dry weight vs turbidity method¹². Residual sugar was determined by DNS method by Miller¹³. The kinetic parameters of ethanol fermentation was followed by Abate *et al.*⁴.

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